

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids : Part III. Thermodynamic Ionisation Constants of N-*p*-Tolyl-*m*-Nitrobenzohydroxamic Acid

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Thermodynamic ionisation constants, TpK_a , of N-*p*-Tolyl-*m*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid have been determined in aqueous dioxane water media (10-70%) at 25° and 35°. The plot of TpK_a vs mole fraction of dioxane is linear in a given temperature.

THE thermodynamic ionisation constants of some hydroxamic acids have been reported previously¹. In the present communication the additional data on the ionisation constants of N-*p*-tolyl-*m*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid at 25° and 35° are given in 10-70% dioxane water media. Since the N-*p*-tolyl-*p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid is insoluble in water the data for aqueous media are computed from the linear plot of TpK_a vs mole fraction of dioxane.

Experimental

The N-*p*-tolyl-*m*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid was prepared as described elsewhere²; m.p. 107° reported 106°. It was recrystallised before use and its purity was checked by elemental analysis, m.p., IR and UV spectra. Dioxane was purified according to Weissberger⁴. Carbonate free potassium hydroxide solution was prepared by Vogel's electrolytic method⁵ and standardised against potassium hydrogen phthalate and diluted to 0.1 M with the solvent medium.

Procedure

The titration procedure was essentially that recommended by Albert and Serjeant⁶. Generally, 0.05 mmol. of N-*p*-tolyl-*m*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid in 47.5 ml of solvent were placed in a three necked titration vessel (thermostated at 25° or 35°) carrying a glass electrode, microburette and a limb of saturated KCl bridge. Nitrogen gas pre-saturated with solvent was passed through the solution which was titrated with 0.1 M KOH in 0.5 ml aliquots and noting the highest appropriate drift free reading on the pH meter.

Calculations

The TpK_a have been determined by pH titration method using glass and saturated calomel electrodes in cells with liquid junction potential. Activity

coefficients needed in this work have been interpolated from the data of Harned and Owen⁷ on the mean molar activity coefficient, γ_{\pm} , of univalent ions (HCl) in dioxane water media at the desired temperature (25° or 35°) and at various ionic strengths, m_{\pm} , assuming that these activity coefficients will be the same for N-*p*-tolyl-*m*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid. The empirical corrections

$$-\log[H^+] = B + \log U^0_H + \log \gamma_{\pm} \quad \dots (1)$$

for medium effect have been applied as suggested by Van Uitert and Hass^{8,9}. The ionisation of the hydroxamic acid, HA in aqueous solution gives hydrogen ion and hydroxamate ion and the equilibrium constant may be

$$K_{a(aq)} = ([H^+][A^-]/[HA]) (\gamma_H + \gamma_A - \gamma_{HA})$$

or

$$TpK_a(aq) = -\log[H^+] + \log([HA]/[A^-]) - 2 \log \gamma_{\pm} \quad \dots (2)$$

assuming γ_{HA} , the activity coefficient of unionized acid is unity. The final form of the equation for calculating the ionisation constants in dioxane water media is obtained from equation (1) and (2)

$$TpK_a = B + \log U^0_H + \log([HA]/[A^-]) - \log \gamma_{\pm}$$

where B is the pH meter reading and the values of the $\log U^0_H$ were determined previously¹⁰

Results

The thermodynamic ionisation constants (TpK_a) at different mole fractions of dioxane at 25° and 35° are given in Table I. The plot of TpK_a 's vs mole fraction of dioxane is linear at a given temperature.

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The empirical relation $pK_a = mn_2 + c$ is obtained by the method of least squares performed with the aid of a CDC 3600 computer are also given in Table 1. It is believed that the pK_a values reported are accurate to ± 0.03 unit.

TABLE I—IONISATION CONSTANTS OF *N-p*-TOLYL-*m*-NITRO-BENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID AT 25° AND 35°

Dioxane v/v %	Mole fraction of dioxane, n_2	TpK _a			
		Temperature 25°		Temperature 35°	
		Expt.	Least squares	Expt.	Least squares
0	0.000	Ins.	8.36	Ins.	8.24
10	0.023	8.64	8.63	8.50	8.51
20	0.050	8.95	8.94	8.83	8.82
30	0.083	9.34	9.33	9.20	9.20
40	0.123	9.82	9.84	9.67	9.67
45	0.147	10.08	10.08	9.96	9.95
50	0.174	10.40	10.39	10.26	10.26
60	0.240	11.17	11.16	11.03	11.03
70	0.330	12.21	12.22	12.07	12.08

25°, $TpK_a = 11.69n_2 + 8.36$; 35° $TpK_a = 11.61n_2 + 8.24$

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